

Tri-ligand Complexes of Some Lanthanons with 1,2-Diaminocyclohexane-N,N,N',N'-tetraacetic Acid and Dicarboxylic Acids

P. C. DWIVEDI, S. P. TRIPATHI and R. C. SHARMA*

Department of Chemistry, Agra University, Agra-282 002

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The formation of hetero-ligand 1 : 1 : 1 : 1 Ln(III)-CDTA-CCA-MLN complexes [Ln(III) = La(III), Pr(III), Nd(III), Gd(III) or Dy(III), CDTA = 1,2-diaminocyclohexane-N,N,N',N'-tetraacetic acid, CCA = citraconic acid and MLN = malonic acid], have been studied in solution potentiometrically. The formation constants ($\log K_{MLL'L''}$) and the free energies of formation (ΔG°) for the resulting mixed-ligand quaternary species have been evaluated at constant ionic strength ($\mu = 0.1 M KNO_3$) and temperature $25 \pm 1^\circ$. The relative order of stabilities observed as La(III) < Pr(III) < Nd(III) < Gd(III) < Dy(III) in terms of metal ions and ternary < quaternary in the case of complex species have been explained.

In recent years, the formation of ternary complexes¹⁻⁵ of lanthanons has been established by different physico-chemical techniques, but the formation of quaternary species has been shown only in a few references^{6,7}. It is interesting to note that during the formation of quaternary mixed-ligand species, the metal ions have a tendency to further expand their coordination and the resulting quaternary species have been found more stable than the ternary ones. This interesting fact led us to investigate some more quaternary systems of lanthanides and in the present paper we report our potentiometric studies on 1 : 1 : 1 : 1 Ln(III)-CDTA-CCA-MLN quaternary systems.

Experimental

The solutions of all the chemicals (A.R., B.D.H. or G.R., E. Merck) used were prepared in double distilled water. Standard solutions of rare earth nitrates^{8,4} and the involved ligands^{6,7} were prepared and standardised as reported earlier.

Potentiometric titrations were carried out with Philips pH-meter (PR 9405 M) against 0.1 M KOH solution keeping the ionic strength ($\mu = 0.1 M KNO_3$), temperature ($25 \pm 1^\circ$) and the total volume constant in the beginning of each titration as previously described⁷.

Calculations :

Formation constants :

The dissociation constants of tripotassium 1,2-diaminocyclohexane-N,N,N',N'-tetraacetate (K_3CDTA) ($pK = 11.22 \pm 0.10$), citraconic acid (CCA) ($pK_1 = 2.42 \pm 0.09$, $pK_2 = 5.88 \pm 0.04$) and malonic acid (MLN) ($pK_1 = 2.69 \pm 0.09$, $pK_2 = 5.75 \pm 0.06$) were evaluated by the method of Chaberek and Martell⁸, formation constants ($\log K_{MLL'L''}$, $\log K_{MLL'L''}$)

of the ternary and quaternary complexes by the modified⁹ method of Ramamoorthy and Santappa⁹ and deprotonation constant ($-\log K_A^H$) in the case of ternary complexes by the method of Dey *et al*¹⁰.

Results and Discussion

Identical curves were obtained in similar systems involving the used metal ions. Hence for the sake of brevity, the curves for 1 : 1 : 1 : 1 La(III)-CDTA-CCA-MLN have only been discussed to explain the formation of ternary and quaternary species.

Curve b showing the titration of tripotassium salt (K_3CDTA) of CDTA may be ascribed to the non-titrable nature of the remaining carboxylic proton of the CDTA as indicated by the absence of an inflection on this curve. Curves c and d, representing the pH-titration of free CCA and MLN, exhibit two inflections at $m = 1$ and $m = 2$, respectively due to the liberation of two carboxylic protons in two distinct steps at different pH.

Binary systems :

Curve e depicts the titration of 1 : 1 La(III)-CDTA. An extensive lowering in the initial pH as compared to the curve b, followed by a well-defined inflection at $m = 1$, may be attributed to the formation of soluble 1 : 1 La(III)-CDTA species⁸.

Curves f/g illustrate the titration of 1 : 1 La(III)-CCA/MLN systems respectively, giving two inflections at $m = 2$ and $m \approx 4$. First inflection at $m = 2$ may be attributed to the formation of 1 : 1 La(III)-CCA/MLN species. The appearance of a white gelatinous precipitate at $m > 2$ followed by another inflection at $m \approx 4$ may be correlated to the disproportionation of the initially formed 1 : 1 species

Fig. 1. System La(III)-CDTA-CCA-MLN.

- b CDTA
- d MLN
- f 1 : 1 ; La(III)-CCA
- h 1 : 1 : 1 ; La(III)-CDTA-CCA
- i 1 : 1 : 1 ; La(III)-CDTA-MLN
- j 1 : 1 : 1 : 1 ; La(III)-CDTA-CCA-MLN
- T Theoretical composite curve
- Appearance of precipitate
- c CCA
- e 1 : 1 ; La(III)-GDTA
- g 1 : 1 ; La(III)-MLN

into 1 : 3 La(III)-CCA/MLN complex¹¹ with the precipitation of the remaining metal as metal hydroxide.

Ternary systems :

During the titration of ternary systems represented by the curves h/i, a fall in the initial pH as compared to the curves, e, f and g and an inflection at m=2 on the curves h/i may be ascribed to the formation of soluble 1:1:1:1 La(III)-CDTA-CCA/MLN mono-protonated ternary species. The deprotonation of these protonated species occurs further in the higher pH range as indicated by the appearance of one more well-defined inflection at m=3. An absence of solid phase throughout the titration and the non-superimposable nature of the curves h/i with either of binary curves e, f or g further substantiate the formation of hetero-ligand ternary species.

Quaternary systems :

Curve j corresponds to the titration of 1 : 1 : 1 : 1 La(III)-CDTA-CCA-MLN quaternary system. A further lowering in the initial pH as compared to that observed in the binary and ternary systems, (curves e, f, g, h and i) and an inflection at m=3 indicate the simultaneous replacement of three carboxylic protons (one from each of the ligands) of the three involved ligands (K_a CDTA, CCA and MLN) and may be ascribed to the formation of 1 : 1 : 1 : 1 La(III)-CDTA-CCA-MLN diprotonated hetero-ligand quaternary species at low pH. The occurrence of one more inflection at m=5 on this curve is probably due to further titration of the remaining carboxylic protons of CCA and MLN resulting in the deprotonation of the initially formed 1 : 1 : 1 : 1 quaternary species of unusual coordination number^{6,7,11-16}. The absence of any precipitate and non-superimposable nature of the theoretical composite curve¹⁷ T (drawn by adding the horizontal distances of curve c and i to the curve j in the region of mixed-ligand complex formation) lend additional support to the above quaternary complex formation :

In the pH range 2.34-3.75, where the calculations for protonated hetero-ligand species have been made, the two dicarboxylic acids (CCA and MLN) probably behave as mono basic acids. The almost negligible values of percentage dissociation of the second proton of the acid, (for CCA=0.735% and MLN=0.99% at pH=3.75), evaluated by the method of Serjeant¹⁸, indicate that the second proton of CCA and MLN remains almost intact in the mentioned pH range.

Formation constants of mixed-species :

The values of formation constants have been given in Table 1. The relative stabilities of the resulting ternary and quaternary species ($\log K_{MLL'}$, $\log K_{MLL''}$ and $\log K_{MLL'L''}$, respectively) in terms of metal ions have been observed in the order La(III) < Pr(III) < Nd(III) < Gd(III) < Dy(III), which is in confirmation of the earlier observations^{3,6,7,11-16} and may be explained on the basis of decreasing size and increasing ionic potential (charge/radius ratio) of lanthanides. In terms of complex species, the order quaternary > ternary may be explained on the basis of the increased number of fused rings¹⁹ and extrastabilization caused by ligand-ligand interactions in quaternary complexes.

Deprotonation constants :

Calculated values of deprotonation constants ($-\log K_A^H$) of the protonated ternary species are

TABLE 1—FORMATION CONSTANTS AND FREE ENERGIES OF FORMATION AT 25 ± 1°

Metal ions	1 : 1 : 1 M(III)-ODTA-CCA/MLN				1 : 1 : 1 : 1 M(III)-ODTA-CCA-MLN	
	CCA		MLN		log K _{M,LL'L} "	ΔG° kcal/mol/ deg
	log K _{M,LL'L} '	ΔG° kcal/mol/ deg	log K _{M,LL'L} "	ΔG° kcal/mol/ deg		
La(III)	12.23 ± 0.15	-16.66	12.87 ± 0.10	-17.54	16.14 ± 0.10	-21.99
Pr(III)	12.37 ± 0.11	-16.86	12.98 ± 0.11	-17.69	16.22 ± 0.12	-22.10
Nd(III)	12.60 ± 0.16	-17.17	13.07 ± 0.12	-17.81	16.38 ± 0.07	-22.32
Gd(III)	12.73 ± 0.12	-17.35	13.26 ± 0.11	-18.07	16.50 ± 0.09	-22.48
Dy(III)	13.00 ± 0.16	-17.71	13.37 ± 0.11	-18.22	16.68 ± 0.09	-22.73

given in Table 2. The lower calculated values of $-\log K_A^H$ in comparison to the pK_2 values of CCA and MLN are of significance and may be attributed to the deprotonation of the ternary species having coordinated dibasic acid. The values of deprotonation constants and percentage ionisation of the ligands (CCA and MLN) calculated in the lower pH range in the case of ternary complexes obviously indicate that only one of the protons of each of the dicarboxylic acids is labile in the lower pH range forming mixed-ligand species. This fact further supports the formation of deprotonated mixed species in quaternary systems in the lower buffer region.

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TABLE 2—DEPROTONATION CONSTANTS OF TERNARY SPECIES AT 25 ± 1°

Metal ions	1 : 1 : 1 M(III)-ODTA-CCA	1 : 1 : 1 M(III)-ODTA-MLN
La(III)	5.88 ± 0.05	5.63 ± 0.06
Pr(III)	5.87 ± 0.05	5.61 ± 0.05
Nd(III)	5.85 ± 0.06	5.59 ± 0.07
Gd(III)	5.83 ± 0.07	5.55 ± 0.07
Dy(III)	5.79 ± 0.06	5.50 ± 0.05

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